

Harnessing Energy in Wireless Fading Channels: Optimized Design Strategies

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Abstract—This paper considers the design of online transmission strategies for slotted energy harvesting point-to-point communication systems in wireless fading channels. Online transmission strategies decide the amount of energy allocated to each transmission slot based on the energy harvested amounts and channel gains observed in the current and previous time slots. Offline strategies, in contrast, assume non-causal knowledge of future energy arrivals and channel gains. We adopt a worst case design objective. For a given online policy, we are interested in computing its *maximum rate gap* that is defined as the difference between the offline and online rates, maximized over all possible energy arrivals and channel states. The *competitive rate gap* is then defined as the minimum maximum rate gap over all possible online strategies. Here, we obtain, within a constant, the maximum rate gap for the Myopic policy, which equally distributes the available energy over the remaining slots, and provide an upper and a lower bound on the competitive rate gap. Moreover, we propose a new online policy targeting the competitive rate gap. Numerical results show that the policy proposed performs close to the competitive rate gap lower bound in constant and arbitrarily varying channels, and obtains good performance with real energy harvesting traces.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Energy harvesting (EH) technology is considered as a major component of future wireless networks. Harvesting energy from the environment extends the lifetime of wireless devices, and provides them untethered mobility, as batteries can be charged without connecting to the power grid infrastructure. However, designing EH communication systems entails its own challenges. For many energy sources, such as solar, vibration or electromagnetic, the characteristics of the EH profile changes over time. The time-varying nature of the available energy motivates the design of transmission strategies that take into account the stochastic nature of the energy arrival process.

The EH process is typically modeled as a set of energy packets arriving at discrete time instants. Previous works addressing the design of transmission policies for EH devices are typically classified based on the assumptions made on the transmitter's knowledge about the EH process [1]. In the *offline optimization* framework the transmitter is assumed to have access to all the future energy packet arrival instants and packet sizes. The offline transmission policy that maximizes the throughput for an EH point-to-point additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) channel was first studied in [2] and, extended to fading channels in [3]. More realistic battery and energy consumption models were considered in [4]–[8], and extension to several multi-terminal communications channels were considered in [9]–[12]. The offline design serves as a theoretical upper bound and has been proven useful in inspiring online policies [3]. However, offline policies are only applicable in practice when the EH process is more or less deterministic, or is random, but can be accurately predicted, as for example with solar panels. The *online optimization* framework, instead, assumes that the future energy arrivals are unknown. If the transmitter has statistical knowledge of the underlying EH process, then, the optimization problem is modeled as a Markov decision process, and the optimal policy can be determined through dynamic programming [1], [13].

Most of the works available in the literature about online optimization show performance results that are very close to those achieved by optimal offline policies [14]. However, it is not yet clear how much of these results can be attributed to the online policy, or to the stochastic model considered for the EH and fading processes. In this work, we adopt a competitive (worst-case) analysis framework. The policies that result from this analysis are universal in a deterministic sense, that is, the observed EH and fading sequences are not assumed to be randomly drawn by some probability law, but they are rather individual, deterministic sequences. Universal strategies in this sense guarantee a worst performance for any possible sequence. The study of universal strategies in a probabilistic sense, this is, for any possible energy arrival distribution, has been recently initiated in [15]–[17] and references there in. Our main objective is to characterize the gap between the optimal offline and online policies. Identifying this gap independently of the EH and fading statistics will determine the value of the knowledge about

these random processes. If the gap between the optimal offline and online policies is significantly large, more effort should be put into learning the behavior of the underlying EH and fading processes [18].

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. The related work and contributions of the paper are given in Section II. The system model is described in Section III. The competitive analysis framework is developed in Section IV. The Myopic upper bound is derived in Section V. The constant channel lower bound is presented in Section VI. Finally, numerical results are presented in Section VII and conclusion are drawn in Section VIII.

II. RELATED WORK AND CONTRIBUTIONS

Resorting to the competitive analysis framework [19], the design of online algorithms for the problem of dynamic power allocation with a sum-energy/power constraint in an arbitrarily varying wireless fading channel was first considered in [20]– [22]. Then, in [23], the authors introduced the competitive analysis of EH communication systems in terms of the *competitive rate ratio*, which is defined as the ratio between the optimal offline rate and online rate, maximized over all channel and energy harvesting sequences and minimized over all possible online policies. [23] shows that the competitive rate ratio is equal to the number of slots, N , and that the *Myopic policy*, which equally distributes the available energy over the remaining slots, is optimal in that sense. Algorithms for time fair energy allocation in systems with deterministic energy inputs were developed in [5]. The related problem of minimizing the transmission time of a fixed number of bits when both the energy arrivals and fading coefficients are arbitrarily varying was considered in [23]. Finally, the framework of online convex optimization has been applied in [24] to design online algorithms capable of learning the optimal policy from the observed energy amounts and channel states in the past. The above works address the case of point-to-point communications, for network of energy harvesting devices, the reader is referred to [25], [26].

As we discuss in detail in section IV-A, the *competitive rate gap* complements the information provided by the competitive rate ratio. Specifically, we show that the competitive rate gap, for which the rate ratio objective is replaced by the rate difference, is upper bounded by $\log_2(N)$ and derive a recursive expression to compute a lower bound on it. The lower bound derivation is based on the evaluation of exponentially increasing energy harvesting sequences, a key idea first introduced in [23]. Additionally, for the Myopic policy, we show that the

maximum rate gap is between $N^{-1}\log_2(N!)$ and $\log_2(N)$, characterizing it within a constant $\log_2(e)$. We next provide a lower bound on the maximum rate gap for fixed fraction policies. For these policies, a constant fraction of the remaining energy in the battery is allocated at every time slot. These policies have been, recently, shown to obtain an average throughput within a constant rate gap of the optimal strategy [15]. Finally, we propose a new online policy targeting the competitive rate gap lower bound. Numerical results show that, for constant channels, the policy proposed performs very close to the competitive rate gap lower bound, and outperforms the Myopic policy. For arbitrarily varying channels, the maximum rate gap obtained by the proposed policy is shown to approach the competitive rate gap lower bound as the number of slots increases. We also provide an numerical evaluation of the policies proposed with real energy harvesting data. Some of these results have appeared in [27], [28] without complete proofs. Additionally, the case of two time slots $N = 2$, was discussed in detail in [29].

III. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a slotted wireless transmission from a source to a destination over an AWGN channel. We assume a block fading model, where the fading coefficients remain constant for the duration of a slot. Let \mathbb{R}_+ denote the set of non-negative real numbers, then $h_n \in \mathbb{R}_+$ denotes the fading coefficient¹ at time slot $n = 1, \dots, N$, where N is the total number of slots. The transmitter harvests energy from the environment over time. The energy harvested during time slot $n - 1$ is only available at the beginning of slot n , and is denoted by $E_n \in \mathbb{R}_+$. Within every slot n , we consider the Shannon capacity function to relate the achieved instantaneous rate to the transmitted power; that is, if the transmission power at time t is $p(t)$ then the instantaneous rate is given by $r(p(t), h_n) = \log_2(1 + h_n p(t))$, where the capacity units are bits per second per Hertz (bps/Hz). Unless otherwise stated all logarithms are in base 2, and we drop the subscript 2 from here onward. Without loss of generality we assume that the duration of a slot and the transmission bandwidth are equal to one, then the total number of bits transmitted over slot n is

$\int_0^1 r(p(t), h_n) dt$. Denote by $U_n \in \mathbb{R}_+$ the energy allocated for transmission during time slot n . Due to the strict concavity of the capacity function, the rate in each slot is maximized by equally distributing the energy U_n over the

¹

whole slot duration. Then, the number of bits transmitted over slot n is found as

$D_n(U_n, h_n) = \log(1 + h_n U_n)$. After N time slots, the rate is

$$R = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \log(1 + h_n U_n) \tag{1}$$

As in [3], [23] and other related works, we assume a simplistic energy consumption model. We consider a fictitious infinite capacity battery that carries energy for only communication purposes. In real life, however, the energy harvested needs to feed also all circuits in the system [5]. Due to the energy causality constraint, the total energy used by the end of slot n cannot be greater than the energy harvested by the beginning of time-slot n , that is

$$\sum_{m=1}^n U_m \leq \sum_{m=1}^n E_m, \quad n = 1, \dots, N. \tag{2}$$

Notation: We denote vectors in bold letters $\mathbf{x} = \{x_n\}_{n=1}^N$ where x_n is the n -th element in \mathbf{x} . Then, vector functions are denoted as $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}) = \{v_n(\mathbf{x})\}_{n=1}^N$ where $v_n(\mathbf{x})$ denotes the n -th function in $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x})$. We use $\mathbf{x}^n = \{x_l\}_{l=1}^n$ and $\mathbf{v}^n(\mathbf{x}) = \{v_l(\mathbf{x})\}_{l=1}^n$ to denote the n -length vector containing the first n elements of \mathbf{x} and $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x})$, respectively. We use indistinguishably $\mathbf{x}_N = \mathbf{x}$ and $\mathbf{v}_N(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x})$.

IV. COMPETITIVE ANALYSIS

Let $\mathbf{E} = \{E_n\}_{n=1}^N$ and $\mathbf{h} = \{h_n\}_{n=1}^N$ denote the energy and channel vectors, respectively. Then, the transmission policy

$\mathbf{U}(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}) = \{U_n(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h})\}_{n=1}^N$ is a vector function of \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{h} , and the achieved rate $R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U})$ in (1) is a function of \mathbf{E} , \mathbf{h} , and the policy adopted \mathbf{U} . The optimal offline policy $\mathbf{U}^{(o)}(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}) = \{U_n^{(o)}(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h})\}_{n=1}^N$ is then the policy that maximizes the rate with complete knowledge of \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{h}

$$R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}^{(o)}) = \max_{\mathbf{U} \in \mathcal{U}^{(o)}} R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U})$$

where $\mathcal{U}^{(o)} = \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}) = \{U_n(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h})\}_{n=1}^N : (2)\}$ denotes the set of feasible offline policies. The offline problem has been widely studied in the literature. An efficient algorithm to compute exactly the optimal offline policy $\mathbf{U}^{(o)}$ was presented in [30] referred to as *staircase water filling* algorithm, and as *directional water-filling* algorithm in [3]. Observe that for offline policies, the energy allocated at time slot n ,

$U_n^{(o)}(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h})$, is a function of the complete energy and channel vectors \mathbf{E} , and \mathbf{h} . In contrast, we refer to online policies

$\mathbf{U}(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}) = \{U_n(\mathbf{E}_n, \mathbf{h}_n)\}_{n=1}^N$ as those policies for which the energy allocated at time slot n , $U_n(\mathbf{E}_n, \mathbf{h}_n)$, only depends on the energy and channel vectors up to time slot n . We

further assume in this work that online policies make no assumption about the statistics of the energy and channel processes.

We define the rate gap associated to the triplet $\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}$ as

$$G(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}) \triangleq R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}^{(o)}) - R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U})$$

For a particular policy \mathbf{U} , we are interested in computing the maximum rate gap over all energy and channel vectors

$$g(\mathbf{U}) = \{U_n(\mathbf{E}_n, \mathbf{h}_n)\}_{n=1}^N : (2)\} \max_{\{\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}\} \in \mathbb{R}_+^{2N}} G(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}) \tag{3}$$

Let $\mathcal{U} = \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h})$ denote the set of feasible online policies. We want to find the online policy $\mathbf{U} \in \mathcal{U}$ that obtains the minimum value of this maximum rate gap. Given that we allow the transmission policy at time slot n , $U_n(\mathbf{E}_n, \mathbf{h}_n)$, to depend on the energy and channel vectors up to time slot n , \mathbf{E}_n and \mathbf{h}_n , we alternate the max-min operations at different slots as

$$g^* = \max_{E_1, h_1} \min_{U_1} \max_{E_2, h_2} \min_{U_2} \dots \max_{E_N, h_N} \min_{U_N} G(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}) \tag{4}$$

where $\{E_n, h_n\} \in \mathbb{R}_+^2$ and $U_n \in \mathcal{U}_n = \{U_n(\mathbf{E}_n, \mathbf{h}_n) : (2)\}$.

Observe that, in the min-max game (4), the online policy at time slot n , U_n , has causal advantage over the energy and channels up to time slot n , \mathbf{E}_n , and \mathbf{h}_n . Similarly, the nature; energy arrivals and channel gains, at time slot n , has causal advantage over the online policy adopted in previous time slots, \mathbf{U}_{n-1} . As an example, consider the case of two slots and constant channels. In this case, solving (4) reduces to

$$\max_{E_1} \min_{U_1} \max_{E_2} \min_{U_2} G(E_1, E_2, U_1, U_2)$$

Given that in max-min/min-max problems, the innermost operations are first applied, we first solve the inner minimization on U_2 for every possible E_1, U_1 , and E_2 , i.e.

$$G_{U_2}(E_1, E_2, U_1) = \min_{U_2} G(E_1, E_2, U_1, U_2)$$

As as a result, we obtain the optimal energy allocation function at time slot 2 as $U_2^*(E_1, E_2, U_1)$. Next, we solve the inner maximization over E_2 , for every possible E_1 and U_1 , i.e.

$$G_{E_2}(E_1, U_1) = \max_{E_2} G_{U_2}(E_1, E_2, U_1)$$

to obtain $E_2^*(E_1, U_1)$. Then, we solve the inner minimization over U_1 for every possible E_1 , i.e.

$$G_{U_1}(E_1) = \min_{U_1} G_{E_2}(E_1, U_1)$$

to obtain the optimal energy allocation function at time slot

1, $U_1^*(E_1)$. Finally, we maximize over the only remaining variable E_1 . Observe that we have obtained the optimal online policy with the desired causality dependence, i.e. $U_1^*(E_1)$ and $U_2^*(E_1, E_2, U_1^*)$.

We attempt to solve (4) by obtaining upper and lower bounds on g^2 . Upper bounds are obtained by solving the maximum rate gap problem in (3) for a particular online policy $\mathbf{U} \in \mathcal{U}$. Then $g^2 \leq g(\mathbf{U})$. For the lower bounds, we solve (4) only over a subset $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_+^{2N}$ of energy and channel vectors,

$$g_S = \max_{E_1, h_1} \min_{U_1} \max_{E_2, h_2} \min_{U_2} \dots \max_{E_N, h_N} \min_{U_N} G(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}) \quad (5)$$

where $\{E_n, h_n\} \in \mathcal{S}_n \subseteq \mathbb{R}_+^2$. Then $g^2 \geq g_S$. Observe that we can solve (5) by solving recursively for $n = N - 1$ to $n = 1$

$$G_n^*(\mathbf{E}_n, \mathbf{h}_n, \mathbf{U}_{n-1}) = \min_{U_n \in \mathcal{U}_n} \max_{\{E_{n+1}, h_{n+1}\} \in \mathcal{S}_{n+1}} G_{n+1}^*(\mathbf{E}_{n+1}, \mathbf{h}_{n+1}, \mathbf{U}_n), \quad (6)$$

with $G_N^*(\mathbf{E}_N, \mathbf{h}_N, \mathbf{U}_{N-1}) = \min_{U_N \in \mathcal{U}_N} G(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U})$. Then,

$$g_S = \max_{E_1, h_1} \min_{U_1} G(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U})$$

Finally, given the inequalities

$$g_S \leq g^2 \leq g(\mathbf{U}) \quad (7)$$

we can conclude that the online policy \mathbf{U} is optimal in terms of the competitive rate gap, if for a particular set \mathcal{S} , we are able to show that $g_S = g(\mathbf{U})$.

A. Competitive rate ratio

The competitive rate gap resembles the competitive rate ratio recently considered in [23] for the same system model considered here, i.e. energy harvesting point-to-point slotted communications over fading channels

$$r = \min_{\mathbf{U} \in \mathcal{U}} \max_{\{\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}\} \in \mathbb{R}_+^{2N}} \frac{R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U})}{R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}^{(o)})}$$

There authors show² that the competitive rate ratio is equal to the number of slots N . Specifically, in [23] authors show that the *Myopic policy*, there referred to as *Repeated Equal Power Allocation (REPA)*, that equally distributes the available energy over the remaining slots,

$$\mathbf{U}^{(m)}(\mathbf{E}) = \left\{ U_n^{(m)}(\mathbf{E}_n) \right\}_{n=1}^N$$

$$U_n^{(m)}(\mathbf{E}_n) = \sum_{l=1}^n \frac{E_l}{N - l + 1}, \quad n = 1, \dots, N \quad (8)$$

is optimal in terms of the competitive rate ratio.

The competitive rate gap considered here complements the information provided by the competitive rate ratio. In particular, observe that the competitive rate ratio, r , and the competitive rate gap, g , guarantee that there is an

online transmission policy \mathbf{U}^r and \mathbf{U}^g , respectively, for which for all vectors \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{h} , it is satisfied that

$$R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}^{(o)}) \leq r R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}_r^*), \quad (9)$$

$$R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}^{(o)}) \leq g + R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}_g^*). \quad (10)$$

We can use these results to have performance guarantees for our online policies. For instance, we could state that the online policy \mathbf{U}^r achieves a fraction r of the offline rate, and that the rate of the online policy \mathbf{U}^g is within g units of the offline rate. We can also use these results to bound the potential rate gains of knowing the

EH and fading processes. Using the fact that $R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}^{(o)})$ is an upper bound on the highest rate that any online policy can achieve, we could state that by learning the EH and fading processes, we could improve the online rate $R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}_g^*)$ by at most g units of information, and the online rate $R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}_r^*)$ by at most $(r - 1)R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}_r^*)$ units.

Establishing a direct relation between both conditions in order to identify which of the two conditions is more restrictive in a particular situation is, however, not yet completely possible. In an attempt to compare both conditions, let us assume

$$R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}_g^*) \simeq R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}_r^*) = R_{rg}(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}),$$

then observe that the rate gap condition (10) is more restrictive than the rate ratio condition (9), if

$$R_{rg}(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}) > \frac{g}{r - 1} \quad (11)$$

or, equivalently, in terms of the offline rate $R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}^{(o)})$, if

$$R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}^{(o)}) > \frac{r}{r - 1} g. \quad (12)$$

There are two main difficulties when attempting to interpret these inequalities. First, we need to decide which is the situation of interest, and know how the online rate $R_{rg}(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h})$, or the optimal offline rate $R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}^{(o)})$ decreases/increases with N in those situations. Second, we need to know how the right-hand side of (11) or (12) decreases/increases with N . Although, we know that $r = N$ from [23], for the competitive rate gap, g , we only have upper and lower bounds. As we show in the following example, depending on which might be the true competitive rate gap, the conclusions could be quite different. For simplicity, let us assume constant channels, EH sequences for which the optimal offline policy achieves a quasi-constant SNR at the receiver. Suppose first that the true competitive rate gap is close to

the $\log_2(N)$ upper bound, then, according to (12), the competitive rate gap is more restrictive than the competitive rate ratio for offline rates satisfying $R(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}^{(o)}) > \frac{N}{N-1} \log_2(N)$. As an example, if

$N = 512$, which assuming time slot of one second corresponds to a continuous transmission of 8 minutes $\frac{N}{N-1} \log_2(N) \simeq 9$

and 20 seconds, we have (, and thus, we require constant SNRs as high as $10 \log_{10}(2^9 - 1) = 27$ dBs. In this case, the utility of the competitive rate gap result is restricted to short transmissions over few slots, or to sites with high energy harvesting capabilities, such as cellular bases stations. Suppose instead, that the true competitive rate gap is close to the lower bound presented in Theorem 2. Then, for $N = 512$, the inequality (12) requires offline rates larger than 1.58, or equivalently, constant received SNRs, as low as, 3dBs. Thus, in this case, the competitive rate gap is more restrictive even for large number of slots, and in low energy harvesting situations. In the numerical results, see Section VII, we show that the true competitive rate ratio is much more close to the lower bound.

Indeed, for constant channels, we have even conjectured that the competitive rate gap coincides with the lower bound.

B. Preliminaries

For our particular choice of a logarithmic rate function (1), the rate gap can be expressed as $G(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}) = -N^\perp \log F(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U})$ with

$$F(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}) = \prod_{n=1}^N \frac{1 + h_n U_n(\mathbf{h}_n, \mathbf{E}_n)}{1 + h_n U_n^{(o)}(\mathbf{h}_n, \mathbf{E}_n)} \tag{13}$$

Given that the function $-\log(\cdot)$ decreases monotonically, the maximum rate gap associated to the policy \mathbf{U} can be obtained as $g(\mathbf{U}) = -N^\perp \log f(\mathbf{U})$ with

$$f(\mathbf{U}) = \min_{(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}) \in \mathbb{R}_+^{2N}} F(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U})$$

Then, we can obtain the competitive rate gap lower bound associated to the set of vectors in S , g_S in (5), by solving, interactively, for $n = N - 1, \dots, 1$

$$F_n^*(\mathbf{E}_n, \mathbf{h}_n, U_{n-1}) = \max_{U_n \in \mathcal{U}_n} \min_{\{E_{n+1}, h_{n+1}\} \in S_{n+1}} F_{n+1}^*(\mathbf{E}_{n+1}, \mathbf{h}_{n+1}, U_n)$$

with $F_N^*(\mathbf{E}_N, \mathbf{h}_N, U_{N-1}) \triangleq \max_{U_N \in \mathcal{U}_N} F(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U})$. Then,

$$f_S = \min_{E_1, h_1} F_1^* \text{ and } g_S = -N^\perp \log f_S.$$

V. MYOPIC UPPER BOUND

In this section, we upper bound g^2 in (4) by upper bounding the Myopic maximum rate gap $g(\mathbf{U}^{(m)})$.

Theorem 1. The competitive rate gap, g^2 , and the Myopic maximum rate gap, $g(\mathbf{U}^{(m)})$, in point-to-point communications over N time slots are upper bounded as

$$g^2 \leq g(\mathbf{U}^{(m)}) \leq \log N.$$

Proof. The Myopic maximum rate gap is given by (see Section

IV-B) $g(\mathbf{U}^{(m)}) = -\frac{1}{N} \log f(\mathbf{U}^{(m)})$ with $f(\mathbf{U}^{(m)}) = \min_{\{\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}\} \in \mathbb{R}_+^{2N}} F(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}^{(m)})$ (14)

and $F(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}^{(m)}) = \prod_{n=1}^N \frac{1 + h_n U_n^{(m)}(\mathbf{h}_n, \mathbf{E}_n)}{1 + h_n U_n^{(o)}(\mathbf{h}_n, \mathbf{E}_n)}$ (15)

We obtain a lower bound on (14). To that end, observe that the energy allocated by the Myopic policy (8) at each time slot n can be lower bounded as $U_n^{(m)}(\mathbf{h}_n, \mathbf{E}_n) \geq \frac{\sum_{l=1}^n E_l}{N}$, whereas any policy, including the optimal offline policy, can allocate at most the total harvested energy up to slot n , this is $U_n^{(o)}(\mathbf{h}_n, \mathbf{E}_n) \leq \sum_{l=1}^n E_l$. Thus, we can lower bound (15) as

$$F(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{U}^{(m)}) \geq \prod_{n=1}^N \frac{1 + h_n \frac{\sum_{l=1}^n E_l}{N}}{1 + h_n \sum_{l=1}^n E_l} \geq \frac{1}{N^N}$$
 (16)

and thus $f(\mathbf{U}^{(m)}) \geq \frac{1}{N^N}$ and $g(\mathbf{U}^{(m)}) = -N^\perp \log f(\mathbf{U}^{(m)}) \leq \log N$. \square

VI. CONSTANT CHANNEL LOWER BOUND

In this section, first, we obtain a lower bound on the competitive maximum rate gap, g^2 , valid for arbitrary varying channel and energy vectors. Then, we particularize the bound for the greedy policy, the Myopic policy and any fixed fraction policy. Finally, we present an online policy which, as shown numerically in Section VII, achieves the competitive rate gap lower bound if channel gains remain constant.

As discussed in Section IV, we can obtain a lower bound on the competitive rate gap by considering a subset of energychannel vectors. Specifically, we consider the subset $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_+^{2N}$ of energy-channel vectors $\{\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}\}$ that results from limiting the channels \mathbf{h} to remain constant over N slots, $\mathbf{h} = \mathbf{1}_N$, and the energy vector to be any of the 2^{N-1} energy vectors

$$\mathbf{E}(E, \mathbf{x}) = \{E_n(E, \mathbf{x})\}_{n=1}^N,$$

$$E_n(E, \mathbf{x}) = \begin{cases} E^n & \text{if } x_n = 1, \\ 0 & \text{if } x_n = 0 \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

with $E \rightarrow \infty$ and $\mathbf{x} = \{x_n\}_{n=1}^N$ with $x_1 = 1$ and $x_n \in \{0,1\}$ for $n = 2, \dots, N$. As an example, for $\mathbf{x} = \{1,0,1,1,0\}$, $\mathbf{E}(E, \mathbf{x}) = \{E, 0, E^3, E^4, 0\}$. Observe that for this particular choice of energy vectors, given that we let $E \rightarrow \infty$, whenever there is an energy arrival at time slot k , this energy arrival is much bigger than any previous energy arrival³. This has very useful consequences in our analysis. As we will show next, for these energy vectors, once there is an energy arrival, the effect of any previous energy arrival on the resource allocation policy adopted in the current and future slots is negligible.

In this section, we rewrite the transmission policy $\mathbf{U}(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h})$ in a more convenient form. Given any online or offline policy $U_n(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h})$, let $\alpha_n(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h})$ be the fraction of the energy stored in the battery at time slot n , B_n , that is used for transmission

$$U_n(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}) = \alpha_n(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h})B_n. \quad (18)$$

Then, we can force the energy causality constraint (2) simply as $\alpha_n(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}) \in (0,1)^{45}$, $n < N$. The battery state at the beginning of time slot n is then given by

$$B_n = B_{n-1} - U_{n-1} + E_n. \quad (19)$$

Using (18) and (19), we can express the energy transmitted at time slot n , as a function of the energy vector \mathbf{E} and the vector of energy fractions up to time slot n , $\alpha_n(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}) = \{\alpha_l(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h})\}_{l=1}^n$, as⁵

$$U_n(\mathbf{E}, \alpha_n(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h})) = \prod_{m=1}^n E_m \prod_{l=m}^{n-1} (1 - \alpha_l(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h})) \quad (20)$$

with $U_0 = 0$. Given that we limit the energy-channel vectors to $\{\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}\} \in \mathcal{S}$ and that, any of these vectors is uniquely determined by a binary vector \mathbf{x} , hereafter, we refer to the energy-fractions associated to the vector \mathbf{x} at slot n , $\alpha_n(\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}), \mathbf{x})$, compactly as $\alpha_n(E, \mathbf{x})$. Moreover, we remove the dependence on E in $\alpha_n(E, \mathbf{x})$ to denote $\alpha_n(\mathbf{x})$, $\lim_{E \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_n(E, \mathbf{x})$.

The next theorem provides the competitive rate gap lower bound, g_S , and the optimal energy fractions $\alpha^*(\mathbf{x}) =$

$$\{\alpha_n^*(\mathbf{x}_n)\}_{n=1}^N \text{ if } \{\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}\} \in \mathcal{S}.$$

Theorem 2. For the particular set of energy-channel vectors in \mathcal{S} , g_S lower bounds the competitive rate gap g^* as

$$g^* \geq g_S = -\frac{1}{N} \log \left(\prod_{n=1}^N \alpha_{n|n}^* \right)$$

where $\alpha_{n|n}^*$ is computed recursively for $n = N$ to $n = 1$ as

$$\alpha_{n|n}^* = 1 - \prod_{s=n+1}^N \alpha_{s|s}^* \Gamma_{s+1-n} \quad (21)$$

with $\Gamma_1 = 1$ and $\Gamma_s = \frac{(s-1)^{s-1}}{s^s}$, $s = 2, \dots, N$.

If $\{\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{h}\} \in \mathcal{S}$, the optimal energy fractions are given by $\alpha^*(\mathbf{x}) = \{\alpha_n^*(\mathbf{x}_n)\}_{n=1}^N$ where $\alpha_n^*(\mathbf{x}_n)$ only depends on the last position of a one in \mathbf{x}_n , $L_1(\mathbf{x}_n)$, as follows: $\alpha_n^*(\mathbf{x}_n) = \alpha_{n|L_1(\mathbf{x}_n)}^*$ with $\alpha_{n|m}^*$ in (21) if $m = n$, and otherwise

$$\alpha_{n|m}^* = \frac{\alpha_{n|n}^* \Gamma_{n+1-m}}{\sum_{s=n}^N \alpha_{s|s}^* \Gamma_{s+1-m}}. \quad (22)$$

Proof. We already know from (7) that g_S lower bounds g^* . In the following, we compute g_S . Let $\mathbf{o}(\mathbf{x}) = \{o_n(\mathbf{x})\}$ denote the vector containing the position of each one in \mathbf{x} , and $\mathbf{z}(\mathbf{x}) = \{z_n(\mathbf{x})\}$ denote the vector containing the number of elements between ones plus one. As an example, for $\mathbf{x} = \{1,0,0,1,0,1\}$, we have $\mathbf{o}(\mathbf{x}) = \{1,4,6\}$, and $\mathbf{z}(\mathbf{x}) = \{3,2,1\}$. Observe that $o_{m+1}(\mathbf{x}) = o_m(\mathbf{x}) + z_m(\mathbf{x})$ for $m \in \{1, \dots, |\mathbf{o}(\mathbf{x})| - 1\}$. For $m = |\mathbf{o}(\mathbf{x})|$, with some abuse of notation, we denote $o_{|\mathbf{o}(\mathbf{x})|+1} = o_{|\mathbf{o}(\mathbf{x})|}(\mathbf{x}) + z_{|\mathbf{o}(\mathbf{x})|}(\mathbf{x})$. We make use of little-o notation. We say that a function $g(x) = o(f(x))$ or, $g(x) \in o(f(x))$ if the growing rate of $f(x)$ as a function of x is much faster than $g(x) = o(f(x))$.

This is, $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{o(f(x))}{f(x)} = 0$.

Following the compact notation introduced earlier, we write the rate $R(\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}), \mathbf{1}, \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{x}, \alpha(\mathbf{x})))$ associated to vector \mathbf{x} , compactly as $R(E, \mathbf{x}, \alpha(E, \mathbf{x}))$. We show in Section A of the supplementary material, that

$$R(E, \mathbf{x}, \alpha(E, \mathbf{x})) = \frac{1}{N} \log(K(E, \mathbf{x}, \alpha(E, \mathbf{x}))) \quad (23)$$

with $K(E, \mathbf{x}, \alpha(\mathbf{x}))$ shown in (24) at the top of the next page.

Minimizing (24) over $\alpha(E, \mathbf{x})$, the optimal offline rate $R(E, \mathbf{x}, \alpha^{(o)}(\mathbf{x}))$ is found in Section B of the supplementary material as (23) with $K(E, \mathbf{x}, \alpha^{(o)}(\mathbf{x}))$ shown in (25).

³
⁴ $R(\mathbf{1}_N, \check{\mathbf{U}}) - R(\mathbf{1}_N, \mathbf{U}) = \frac{2}{N} \log\left(1 + \frac{n-1}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{N} \log(1 + U_{n-1}) \geq 0$
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Next, introducing causality in the rate expression (23), by using $\alpha_n(E, \mathbf{x}_n)$ instead of $\alpha_n(E, \mathbf{x})$, we can evaluate $F(\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}), \mathbf{1}, \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{x}, \alpha(\mathbf{x})))$, or compactly $F(\mathbf{x}, \alpha(\mathbf{x}))$, by letting $E_1 \rightarrow \infty$, as $F(\mathbf{x}, \alpha(\mathbf{x})) = \lim_{E \rightarrow \infty} \frac{K(E, \mathbf{x}, \alpha(E, \mathbf{x}))}{K(E, \mathbf{x}, \alpha^{(0)}(E, \mathbf{x}))}$ to obtain (26).

Recall that conditions $\alpha_n \in (0, 1)$ and $x_n \in \{0, 1\}$ are equivalent to $U_n \in U_n$ and $\{E_n, h_n\} \in S_n$, respectively. Thus, (see Section IV-B), we can obtain the competitive rate gap lower bound, g_S , by solving for $n = N - 1, \dots, 1$

$$F_n^*(\mathbf{x}_n, \alpha_{n-1}(\mathbf{x}_{n-1})) = \max_{\alpha_n \in (0, 1)} \min_{x_{n+1} \in \{0, 1\}} F_{n+1}^*(\mathbf{x}_{n+1}, \alpha_n(\mathbf{x}_n)) \quad (27)$$

with $F_N^*(\mathbf{x}_N, \alpha_{N-1}(\mathbf{x}_{N-1})) = \max_{\alpha_N \in (0, 1]} F(\mathbf{x}, \alpha(\mathbf{x}))$. Then $f_S = F_1^*(1) = \min_{x_1=1} F_1^*(x_1)$ and $g_S = -N \log f_S$. For $n = N$, observe that $F(\mathbf{x}, \alpha(\mathbf{x}))$ increases linearly with $\alpha_N^2(\mathbf{x}_N)$, and thus choosing $\alpha_N^2(\mathbf{x}_N) = 1$ maximizes $F(\mathbf{x}, \alpha(\mathbf{x}))$ for any vector \mathbf{x}_N . We solve (27) for $n = N - 1, \dots, 1$ in Section C of the supplementary material, and show that the solution is always found in the equality of the two terms in the inner minimization, namely

$$F_{n+1}^*(\{\mathbf{x}_n, 1\}, \{\alpha_n(\mathbf{x}_n), \alpha_n^2(\mathbf{x}_n)\}) = F_{n+1}^*(\{\mathbf{x}_n, 0\}, \{\alpha_n(\mathbf{x}_n), \alpha_n^2(\mathbf{x}_n)\}) \quad (28)$$

obtaining $\alpha^2(\mathbf{x})$ as expressed in Theorem 2. (28) implies that

$$F_n^*(\mathbf{x}_n, \alpha_n(\mathbf{x}_n)) = F_{n+1}^*(\mathbf{x}_{n+1}, \{\alpha_n(\mathbf{x}_n), \alpha_n^2(\mathbf{x}_n)\})$$

for $n = 1, \dots, N$, which in turns implies that $F_1^*(1) = F(\mathbf{x}, \alpha^2(\mathbf{x})) = F(\mathbf{y}, \alpha^2(\mathbf{y}))$ for all \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} , and thus by choosing $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{1}_N$, we can obtain f_S as

$$f_S = F_1^*(1) = F(\mathbf{1}_N, \alpha(\mathbf{1}_N)) = \prod_{n=1}^N \alpha_n^2(\mathbf{1}_n) = \prod_{n=1}^N \alpha_n^2|_n$$

concluding the proof. \square

The following corollaries follow from the proof of Theorem 2. The first corollary highlights the need to carefully design online policies in order to have a bounded maximum rate gap.

Corollary 2.1. *The greedy policy $\mathbf{U}^{(e)} = \{U_n^{(e)}\}_{n=1}^N$, which uses all the available energy in the next slot $U_n^{(e)}(\mathbf{E}_n, \mathbf{h}_n) = E_n$, or, equivalently, $\alpha_n^{(e)}(\mathbf{E}_n, \mathbf{h}_n) = 1$ for all n , has an unbounded maximum rate gap, $g(\mathbf{U}^{(e)}) = \infty$.*

Proof. Consider the set S of energy-channel vectors defined previously. Observe that particularizing $F(\mathbf{x}, \alpha(\mathbf{x}))$ in (26) with $\alpha_n^{(e)}(\mathbf{x}_n) = 1$ for all n , we obtain $F(\mathbf{1}_N, \alpha^{(e)}(\mathbf{1}_N)) = 1$ and $F(\mathbf{x}_N, \alpha^{(e)}(\mathbf{x}_N)) = 0$ for all $\mathbf{x}_N \neq \mathbf{1}_N$. Consequently,

$$f_S(\mathbf{U}^{(e)}) = \min_{\mathbf{x}_N} F(\mathbf{x}_N, \alpha^{(e)}(\mathbf{x}_N)) = 0$$

and thus, the maximum rate gap for the greedy policy satisfies $g(\mathbf{U}^{(e)}) \geq -\frac{1}{N} \log f_S(\mathbf{U}^{(e)}) = \infty$. \square

In the next corollary we characterize the Myopic maximum rate gap to within a constant.

Corollary 2.2. *The Myopic maximum rate gap $g(\mathbf{U}^{(m)})$ for arbitrary varying energy-channel vectors satisfies*

$$\log N \geq g(\mathbf{U}^{(m)}) \geq \frac{1}{N} \log N!, \quad (29)$$

$$\geq \log N - \log e. \quad (30)$$

Proof. The upper bound on $g(\mathbf{U}^{(m)})$ was presented in Theorem 1. To obtain the lower bound in (29), we compute the constant channel lower bound on the Myopic maximum rate gap as $g_S(\mathbf{U}^{(m)}) = -\frac{1}{N} \log f_S(\mathbf{U}^{(m)})$, by solving

$$f_S^{(m)} = \min_{\mathbf{x}_N} F(\mathbf{x}_N, \alpha^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}_N))$$

where $F(\mathbf{x}_N, \alpha^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}_N))$ results from particularizing (26) with the Myopic policy in (8). First, observe that the Myopic policy in terms of the energy fractions, reads $\alpha^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}) = \{\alpha_n^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}_n)\}_{n=1}^N$ where $\alpha_n^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}_n) = \frac{1}{N-n+1}$ is independent of vector \mathbf{x}_n . Then, observe that for $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{1}_N$

$$F(\mathbf{1}_N, \alpha^{(m)}) = \prod_{n=1}^N \alpha_n^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}_n) = \frac{1}{N!}. \quad (31)$$

For any other vector, define $w_m(\mathbf{x}) = z_m(\mathbf{x}) + o_m(\mathbf{x}) - 1$. Then, particularizing (26), we have $F(\mathbf{x}, \alpha^{(m)})$

$$= F(\mathbf{1}_N, \alpha^{(m)}) \prod_{m=1}^{|\mathbf{o}(\mathbf{x})|} z_m(\mathbf{x})^{z_m(\mathbf{x})} \prod_{l'=1}^{z_m(\mathbf{x})-1} (1 - \alpha_{w_m(\mathbf{x})-l'}^{(m)})^{l'} \quad (32)$$

$$= \frac{1}{N!} \prod_{m=1}^{|\mathbf{o}(\mathbf{x})|} z_m(\mathbf{x})^{z_m(\mathbf{x})} \prod_{l'=1}^{z_m(\mathbf{x})-1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{N - (w_m(\mathbf{x}) - l') + 1}\right)^{l'} \quad (33)$$

$$\geq \frac{1}{N!} \prod_{m=1}^{|\mathbf{o}(\mathbf{x})|} z_m(\mathbf{x})^{z_m(\mathbf{x})} \prod_{l'=1}^{z_m(\mathbf{x})-1} \left(\frac{l'}{l'+1}\right)^{l'} \quad (34)$$

$$= \frac{1}{N!} \prod_{m=1}^{|\mathbf{o}(\mathbf{x})|} z_m(\mathbf{x})^{z_m(\mathbf{x})} \frac{(z_m(\mathbf{x}) - 1)!}{z_m(\mathbf{x})^{z_m(\mathbf{x})-1}}$$

$$= \frac{1}{N!} \prod_{m=1}^{|\mathbf{o}(\mathbf{x})|} z_m(\mathbf{x})!$$

$$\geq \frac{1}{N!} \quad (35)$$

where to write (32) from (26), we have used the change of variable $l = w_m(\mathbf{x}) - l'$. In equality (33) we particularize

$\alpha_n^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}_n)$. Inequality (34) follows since $w_m(\mathbf{x}) \leq N$, and inequality (35) follows since $z_m(\mathbf{x}) \geq 1$. Then, we have

$$f_S^{(m)} = F\left(\mathbf{1}_N, \alpha^{(m)}\right) = \frac{1}{N!},$$

and the lower bound (29) follows from $g_S^{(m)} = \frac{1}{N} \log N!$. The lower bound in (30) follows by applying the Stirling lower bound $N! \geq \sqrt{2\pi} N^{(N+\frac{1}{2})} e^{-N}$. \square

$$K(E, \mathbf{x}, \alpha(\mathbf{x})) = \prod_{n=1}^N \alpha_n(E, \mathbf{x}) \prod_{m=1}^{|\alpha(\mathbf{x})|} E^{o_m(\mathbf{x})z_m(\mathbf{x})} \prod_{l=o_m(\mathbf{x})}^{o_{m+1}(\mathbf{x})-2} (1 - \alpha_l(E, \mathbf{x}))^{o_{m+1}(\mathbf{x})-l-1} + o\left(\prod_{m=1}^{|\alpha(\mathbf{x})|} E^{o_m(\mathbf{x})z_m(\mathbf{x})}\right) \quad (24)$$

$$K(E, \mathbf{x}, \alpha^{(o)}(\mathbf{x})) = \prod_{m=1}^{|\alpha(\mathbf{x})|} \left(\frac{E^{o_m(\mathbf{x})}}{z_m(\mathbf{x})}\right)^{z_m(\mathbf{x})} + o\left(\prod_{m=1}^{|\alpha(\mathbf{x})|} E^{o_m(\mathbf{x})z_m(\mathbf{x})}\right) \quad (25)$$

$$F(\mathbf{x}, \alpha(\mathbf{x})) = \prod_{n=1}^N \prod_{m=1}^{|\alpha(\mathbf{x})|} \alpha_n^{z_m(\mathbf{x})} \prod_{l=o_m(\mathbf{x})}^{o_{m+1}(\mathbf{x})-1} (1 - \alpha_l(\mathbf{x})) \quad (26)$$

Observe that since the lower bound in (29) was obtained assuming constant channels, from Corollary 2.2, we can also conclude that the maximum rate gap for the Myopic policy in fading or constant channels differ no more than $\log e = 1,442$.

The next corollary, provides a lower bound on the rate gap for any fixed fraction policy, this is, policies allocating at every time slot a constant fraction q of the remaining energy in the battery $U_n = qB_n$, or, equivalently $\alpha_n(\mathbf{x}_n) = q$ for all n . These strategies have been shown in [15] to obtain an average throughput within a constant rate gap of the optimal online strategy.

Corollary 2.3. *For any fixed fraction policy $\mathbf{U}^{(q)}$, with $U_n = qB_n$, the maximum rate gap $g(\mathbf{U}^{(q)})$ for arbitrary varying energy-channel vectors satisfies*

$$g(\mathbf{U}^{(q)}) \geq -\log\left(1 - N^{-\frac{2}{N-1}}\right), \quad (36)$$

Proof. We can reuse the analysis conducted in the proof of Corollary 2.2. Consider the input sequences $\mathbf{x}^{(1)} = \mathbf{1}_N$ and $\mathbf{x}^{(0)} = [1, \mathbf{0}_{N-1}]$, particularizing (31) and (32) for $\alpha_n(\mathbf{x}_n) = q$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} F(\mathbf{x}^{(1)}, q) &= q^N, \\ F(\mathbf{x}^{(0)}, q) &= q^N N^N (1 - q)^{\frac{(N-1)N}{2}} \end{aligned}$$

where we have use the facts that $\mathbf{z}(\mathbf{x}^{(0)}) = N, \mathbf{0} \mathbf{x}^{(n)} = 1$ and $\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} i = \frac{(N-1)N}{2}$. Next, observe that $f_S(\mathbf{U}^{(q)})$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \max_{\mathbf{x}_N} \min_{q \in (0,1)} F(\mathbf{x}_N, q) \\ &\leq \max_{q \in (0,1)} \min_{\mathbf{x}^{(1)}, \mathbf{x}^{(0)}} F(\mathbf{x}_N, q) \end{aligned}$$

$= (q^*)^N$
 $1 - q^* = N^{-\frac{2}{N-1}}$
 with $\left(\begin{matrix} * \\ * \end{matrix}\right)$. Consequently, $g(\mathbf{U}^{(q)}) \geq -\log f_S(\mathbf{U}^{(q)}) \geq -\log q^*$. \square

A. Online Constant Channel Policy

The derivation of the competitive rate gap lower bounds provides insights on the design of good online policies. We know from Corollary 2.1 that using the greedy policy is not a good idea if we are concerned about worst case performance. Corollary 2.2 provides us competitive rate gap guarantees for the Myopic policy and from the proof of Corollary 2.3,

TABLE I
 LOOK-UP TABLE FOR THE ONLINE POLICY WITH $N = 5$

m	$\alpha_1 m$	$\alpha_2 m$	$\alpha_3 m$	$\alpha_4 m$	$\alpha_5 m$
1	0.5862	0.3730	0.3794	0.4912	1
2		0.6173	0.4340	0.5130	1
3			0.6644	0.5586	1
4				0.7500	1
5					1

we have a potentially good fixed fraction policy candidate $\mathbf{U}^{(q^*)} = \{U_n^{(q^*)}\}_{n=1}^N$ with $U_n^* = q^*B_n$ and $q^* = 1 - N^{-\frac{2}{N-1}}$, which we shall evaluate numerically in next section. Moreover, observe that if the energy-channel vectors are limited to those considered in this section, then we know that the optimal online policy in terms of the competitive rate gap consist on choosing at time slot n , $\alpha_n(\mathbf{x}_n) = \alpha_{n|L(\mathbf{x}_n)}$ as defined in Theorem 2. Observe that $\alpha_{n|m}$, for all $m \leq n$, and $n = 1, \dots, N$ can be pre-computed and stored in a look-up table, as done in Table I for $N = 5$.

Motivated by this online policy, next, we propose a simple online policy designed to approach the competitive gap lower bound for arbitrary varying energy arrivals $\mathbf{E} \in R_+^N$ and constant channels. For this online policy $\mathbf{U}^{(c)} = \{U_n^{(c)}\}_{n=1}^N$, at any time slot n , $U_n^{(c)} = \alpha_n^{(c)}(\mathbf{E}_n)B_n$, where B_n is the energy in the battery at time slot n ,

and where $\alpha_n^{(c)}(\mathbf{E}_n)$ is chosen as one of the n possible energy fractions $\alpha_{n|m}$, $m = 1, \dots, n$ defined in (21) and (22).

In particular, at time slot $n = 1$, we choose $\alpha_1^{(c)}(E_1) = \alpha_{1|1}$ for all E_1 . At time slot $n > 1$, suppose that $\alpha_{n-1}(\mathbf{E}_{n-1}) = \alpha_{n|m}$, then the policy evaluates the condition

$$E_n \geq \frac{\bar{E}_{n,m}}{2} \tag{37}$$

where $\bar{E}_{n,m} = \frac{1}{n-m+1} \sum_{l=m}^n E_l$ is the average observed harvested energy since slot m , when condition (37) was satisfied for the last time, and selects

$$\alpha_n^{(c)}(\mathbf{E}) = \begin{cases} \alpha_{n|n} & \text{if (37) satisfied,} \\ \alpha_{n-1} & \text{if (37) not satisfied,} \\ \alpha_{n|m} & \text{if (37) not satisfied, } m < n \end{cases}$$

otherwise.

VII. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In the numerical results, we first validate the rate gap bounds obtained by computing the maximum rate gaps

Fig. 1. Competitive rate gap analysis: constant channels (left) and fading channels (right).

for arbitrarily energy harvesting and channel sequences. We then study the performance of the online strategies discussed, first with uniform energy harvesting amounts and Rayleigh fading channel gains, and then with real energy harvesting traces from the CRAWDA database [31] and constant channels.

First, we evaluate the maximum rate gap as the number of slots increases. We limit the energy harvesting amounts and channel gains to the discrete set $\{0, 10^{1/10}, 10^{2/10}, \dots, 10^0, 10^1, \dots, 10^8\}$. Due to the exponentially increasing number of possible sequences with the number of slots, N , we limit the analysis to $N \leq 6$. We compute the maximum rate gap obtained with the Myopic policy $U^{(m)}$, the fixed fraction policy found in the proof of

Corollary 2.3, $U^{(q^*)} = \{U_n^{(q^*)}\}_{n=1}^N$ with $U_n^* = q^* B_n$ and $q^* = 1 - N^{-\frac{2}{N-1}}$, and the constant channel policy $U^{(c)}$ presented in Section VI-A. We omit the maximum rate

gap for the greedy policy, as we know from Corollary 2.1 that it is unbounded. Additionally, we depict the Myopic constant channel lower bound presented in Corollary 2.2, the lower bound for fixed fraction policies presented in Corollary 2.3, and the Myopic upper bound $\log N$. Observe that for constant channels, Fig. 1 (left), the proposed online strategy $U^{(c)}$ achieves the competitive rate gap lower bound for all the range shown in the figure. Moreover, the proposed fixed fraction policy $U^{(q)}$ achieves the competitive rate gap lower bound for fixed policies, and the Myopic policy achieves the Myopic lower bound in Corollary 2.2. This numerical results invites us to conjecture that, for constant channels, these lower bounds are tight. For arbitrarily varying channels, Fig. 1 (right), we can observe that for the proposed policy $U^{(c)}$ there is a performance gap with the competitive rate gap lower bound which decreases as the number of transmission slots increases (for $N = 2$, the gap between the $g(U^{(c)})$ and the constant channel lower bound is around 0.8, whereas for $N = 6$ is already less than 0.7). Similarly, there is a rate gap between the proposed fixed

fraction policy and the rate gap lower bound for fixed fraction policies. Interestingly, the Myopic policy still achieves the Myopic constant channel lower bound.

Next, the energy harvesting process is set to as a nonnegative uniform random variable with maximum valued E^- . We assume a Rayleigh fading channel with a channel SNR,

$SNR_c = 10$ dBs. For an energy arrival rate of λ_E Joule/s

Fig. 2. Average rate gap as a function of the number of slots for an uniform energy arrival ($P = -5$ dBW) and Rayleigh fading ($SNR_c = 10$ dB).

Fig. 3. Energy harvesting traces from [31].

(Watts), given that we assume no power outages, the average transmitted power is $P = \frac{\bar{E}}{2T_s} = \lambda E$. We consider the duration of a time-slot $T_s = 1$ s. In addition to the online policies considered in previous figures, here we include the greedy policy introduced in Corollary 2.1 and a fixed fraction policy $\mathbf{U}^{(q_2)}$ with $q_2 = \frac{\mathbb{E}[E_n]}{\bar{E}}$ motivated by the fixed fraction policy proposed in [15]. Observe, that as opposed to the rest of the online policies considered in this work, the fixed fraction policy $\mathbf{U}^{(q_2)}$ assumes that the average and maximum energy arrival are known. In this case, we evaluate the average rate gap as a function of the number of slots. For each number of slots, N , we generate 10^5 independent EH sequences of length N . We fix the energy arrival rate to $P = -5$ dBW (0.3162W) which corresponds to a solar panel of dimensions 100cm^2 and 10% efficiency⁶. The effective average received $SNR = SNR_c P$ is thus 5 dBs. Fig. 2 shows the average rate gap obtained by each of the online policies. The obtained rate

gap results are slightly lower than what we could have expected from our theoretical results, mainly, because the energy arrivals are now bounded to $[0, E^-]$. It is interesting to observe that only after a sufficiently large number of slots, the fixed fraction policy $\mathbf{U}^{(q_2)}$, which assumes that $\mathbb{E}[E_n]$ and E^- are known, obtains a better performance than the constant policy, $\mathbf{U}^{(c)}$, here proposed. Similar conclusions are obtained at lower or higher SNRs.

Finally, consider the real energy harvesting traces online available at [31]. These data traces, depicted in Fig. 3, consist of short-term (around one hour) power density measurements conducted every 30 seconds by sensor devices as they were moving around New York city in four different situations. As in previous simulations, we assume a solar panel of 100 cm^2 and 10% efficiency. In Fig. 4, we evaluate the average rate gap in each situation. To that end, we average the results over all possible continuous time intervals with a fixed duration of $N/2$ minutes. We can think of the Myopic and the Greedy policies as two extreme cases. The Greedy policy spends all the energy as soon as it is available, which is close to optimal for quasi-constant energy arrival processes. Instead, for the Myopic policy, at each time slot, the energy available at the battery is distributed uniformly among all the remaining slots, ensuring energy availability even in the absence of any future energy arrival. Consequently, the Myopic policy performs close to optimal in ON-OFF scenarios in which abundant energy harvested intervals are followed by low energy harvesting intervals, and vice-versa. The proposed policy is designed to work well in any possible scenario. Observe in Fig. 3 that for the mobile-indoor-outdoor and the mobile-communte scenarios, the energy harvesting sequences follows the ON-OFF pattern. In this case, as expected, the Myopic policy improves all other strategies. Observe that the performance of the Proposed policy is found almost exactly in between the Myopic and the Greedy policies performance. On the contrary, observe in Fig. 3, that for the mobile-car and mobile-nyt-nighttime scenarios, the energy harvesting process is very stable. In this situation, the Myopic policy performance is significantly worst than the Greedy policy performance. as expected, while the Proposed policy improves over the Greedy policy.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

We studied the competitive rate gap for energy harvesting communication systems in wireless fading

⁶ Power density for ambient light $31,62\text{ mW/cm}^2$

channels. We first formulated the competitive rate gap problem to capture the causal dependence of the online policy on previous energy arrivals and channel gains. Then, we upper bounded the competitive rate gap by showing that the Myopic maximum rate gap is upper bounded by $\log(N)$. To lower bound the competitive rate gap, we derived a recursive expression lower bounding the competitive rate gap. We also characterized the Myopic maximum rate gap to within the constant $\log e$ by lower bounding it with $N \log(N)$. Then, we proposed an online policy targeting the competitive rate gap in constant channel situations. We validated our results numerically and observed that the maximum rate gap are very close to the lower bounds derived in arbitrarily varying and constant channel situations. Finally, we evaluated the proposed policies using real energy harvesting traces.

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Fig. 4. Results for real harvested energy traces from [31]. From top-left to bottom-right: Pedestrian walking in New York City at daytime ($SNR_c = 10$ dB). Car-based roadtrip ($SNR_c = 10$ dB). Commuting on public transportation ($SNR_c = 20$ dB). Pedestrian walking in New York City at nighttime ($SNR_c = 20$ dB).

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